

HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article analyzes the historical features of the emergence and development of the system of vocational education, i.e. technical schools, their functional and planning solution. At this stage there was a need to return technical schools, i.e. secondary specialized education and provide specialists of secondary specialized level.

Keywords: historical features, analysis, technical schools, education, maktab, progressive methods, the Middle Ages.

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No610 of 2019 - "On measures to improve the efficiency of training mid-level specialists". This resolution defines important aspects of financing and the organization of the educational process in technical schools, as well as the role of state bodies in ensuring the quality of vocational education. [1]

These reforms are aimed at increasing the level of training and improving the system of secondary specialized education in the country, which is an urgent and important part of the development of the economy of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, in the study of a scientific topic, it is necessary to reveal the history of the emergence and creation of technical schools (vocational school, vocational school). [2]

Issues of enlightenment and education in Turkestan. Until 1917, political power was concentrated in the hands of several ruling families and clans, relying on the support of the military. The Muslim clergy, in addition to religious activities, performed certain functions in educating the population and resolving legal issues. The rest of society consisted of merchants, artisans, as well as peasants, who made up the bulk of the population.

In 1917-18, regional councils of public education began to be created, and local councils of public education began to be created in the regions.

In May 1918, the Turkestan Republic began, as it announced, the creation of a new public school. Free education was introduced, entrance exams were canceled, and education was conducted in the native language.

In Turkestan from 1920 to 1925, the state set itself the task of organizing and strengthening a new school, involving as many children of working people as possible, introducing new ideological content into schools everywhere, and training new cadres of teachers.

Tashkent. The building of the general meeting was converted into a technical school. 1921.

About maktab and madrasahs, there was the following measure: they were deprived of state funding. There were no religious subjects in public schools. There were not enough teachers and textbooks. Uzbek textbooks began to be created. Rahimi's primer was created, which was very popular in elementary school. It began to teach children to read and write in the Uzbek language. Textbooks on mathematics, elementary geography, a "primer for adults", and the anthology "Turkic School" (translated from Tatar) appeared. [3]

In 1922, the publication of textbooks increased. Textbooks were given out free of charge, on the condition that they would later be returned safe and sound. The interesting experience of many schools has been preserved. For example, the schools in Fergana, where Khamza, Kori-Niyazov and other graduates of these schools worked, played a role in the development of pedagogical thought.

In the same period, schools began to open in which children deprived of parents studied. Among the teachers there were many enthusiasts of their work, energetically introducing new progressive methods of teaching children.

At the age of 18, after a short training (1 year in a Russian-native school and 3 years in a madrasah), Akilkhon Sharafutdinov organized the first primary school with 70 pupils in Toy-Tyube. He was one of the best teachers-methodologists in primary school, became the initiator of subject education, education of students in diligence and labor skills. writing and arithmetic, worked in the garden, published a wall newspaper, collected seeds, painted. Sharafutdinov was the author

of a number of textbooks and a primer, which went through about 20 editions.

Of great importance in the organization of educational work and the provision of methodological assistance to teachers were the schools established in 1919-1928 in Tashkent on Besh-Agach, I and II levels named after Alman with a boarding school at it. Classes here were held in well-equipped classrooms. Music, drama, radio classes, etc. were created at the school.

In 1921, the school was renamed the Experimental Labor School, and then transformed into a school campus. In addition to the nine-year school, a kindergarten was organized in the town, pedagogical and agricultural classes were opened with a two-year course of study as a technical school. The main attention at the school was paid to the issues of polytechnicization and preparation of students for work.

In 1920, the First Congress of Educators was held, where important issues related to the development of education were raised.

In the 1920s and 1930s, Uzbekistan began to actively open technical schools, the task of which was to train workers and technical specialists in various fields - from agriculture and industry to health care and education.

The history of technical schools in Uzbekistan is closely connected with the process of modernization of education, which began in the Soviet period. After the October Revolution of 1917 in Russia and the formation of the Uzbek SSR in 1924, there was a need to develop a system of vocational education to train qualified personnel for various sectors of the economy.

Chirchik Industrial Technical School

In the 1920s and 1930s, Uzbekistan began to actively open technical schools, the task of which was to train workers and technical specialists in various fields - from agriculture and industry to health care and education. [4]

In connection with the need to provide qualified labor for the needs of the developing capitalist industry and the construction of railways, craft classes (carpentry, turning, bookbinding, and shoemaking) were opened at city schools. They were of great importance for raising the general educational and technical level of education of the population. The growth of trade and intermediary operations caused the opening of evening courses

Between 1975 and 1976 there were 4.8 million pupils in 10,000 general-education schools of all kinds, 117,000 pupils in 273 vocational-technical educational institutions (including 43,000 pupils in 88 vocational-technical educational institutions providing secondary education), 185,200 pupils in 187 specialized secondary educational institutions, and 246,600 pupils in 42 higher educational institutions.

A great contribution to the development of education was made by such teachers and figures as A. Shakuri, Hamza, Abdulla Avloni, Sadriddin Ayni, T.N. Kori-Niyazov, Ismatulla Rakhmatullaev and others.

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First classes at vocational schools

Tashkent. The building of the vocational school

In 1989, more than 500 vocational and technical schools were operating in Uzbekistan.

Military School in Tashkent

Vocational school in Tashkent

Architectural and planning part of the historical period. Technical schools were mainly located in administrative buildings or in adapted buildings, like many educational institutions of the East, arose as an ideological, religious and educational one with a central core in the form of a mosque, where the main educational processes took place.

As a result of the study, it turned out that in the vast territory of Uzbekistan in the early Middle Ages there were independent architectural and artistic schools with established traditions of housing construction, typology of civil, religious and engineering structures. [5]

Conclusion

The historical prerequisites for the formation of vocational education in Uzbekistan, the contribution of Eastern thinkers to the development of vocational training, the scientific heritage of encyclopedic scientists of the Renaissance of the East, a number of qualities that serve as criteria for a perfect, creative personality of the younger generation, according to the teachings of Eastern thinkers, played a huge role in the development of the state.

One of the key features of the secondary vocational education system in Uzbekistan was the linking of educational institutions to specific sectors of the economy. Technical schools were created on the basis of existing enterprises, collective farms and state farms, which made it possible to carry out training as close as possible to real practice and the needs of the economy. This corresponded to the requirements of society in the practice of training personnel in close connection with production.

Restoration and expansion of the network of technical schools: In 2019, it was decided to return to

the system of technical schools for the training of qualified mid-level specialists. The President signed a decree according to which many technical schools were restored and modernized so that they could meet the requirements of the modern economy. This step was a reaction to the need to train specialists for rapidly developing industries such as industry, agriculture, IT, construction and services.

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